

Porygon: A Value-Added Models Factor for C2C2B

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Abstract

PoryGON2 is a value-added models factor for consumer-to-consumer-to-business (C2C2B) storage, trade, and exchange networks based on security software to protect inter-hospital patient information distribution. We describe the process of modifying the program to handle C2C2B type information exchange and use a simulated stock market with a central business and 10000 consumers to test the effects of the software relative to a simulation in its absence. Effects on business profitability were significantly and consistently positive, and the software at no point showed signs of reduced performance at the maximum operational demands of the simulation. PoryGON's utility as a digital adjuvant to C2C2B networks is demonstrated and elaborated on.

Keywords: C2C2B; Financial software; Computation; Pokémon; Publication ethics

Introduction

The consumer-to-consumer-to-business (C2C2B) model is a newly defined model in which a community bridges the gap between the producer and target consumers to facilitate purchasing and expand the volume of trade [1]. Primary examples include the use of Instagram 'influencers' as a means for a brand to reach a wider audience, or scientists inviting peers to submit to "special issues" of journals as a means for the latter to earn more submissions [2,3]. The use of digital storage and transactions, such as the sharing of music online or the trading of Pokémon between through the Nintendo® Global Trade System [4,5], would also count under this model. It is not without its perils, as exemplified by the collapse of the Silph Co.* [SLPH] stock in 2013 after the Dubious_Disk virus corrupted their trade servers, causing millions of dollars in misdirected C2C transactions that the company ultimately had to account for [5,6]. Pocket to pocket companion trading through digital means is currently limited by the requirement of consumers to communicate with each other directly, ideally being close enough together to do this verbally, which is not compatible with the C2C2B model that has a global and impersonal outlook [2,7].

A novel models factor, PoryGON, has been designed to counteract this problem [8]. This program was initially designed for use with the Matcha City hospital in Japan, as a means of delivering an antivirus patch to patient-to-patient information transfer system corrupted with the Jesse/James virus [9]. The software has further applications which researchers are slowly understanding and developing [10], with several noting its potential applications for use in aeronautics and aviation such as space-flight ready drones [11,12].

In this manuscript, we describe the use of PoryGON to facilitate C2C2B transactions, as has been described for past business-minded software [5,13-15]. We intend the model to be rapidly disseminated through PC-to-PC servers connecting consumers to each other [16], and further propose and here demonstrate how the software can bring business into the system to maximize secure and profitable transactions [17].

Methods

PoryGON's base code is available open-source from GitHub [18-20]. Briefly, a Conversion factor algorithm firstly designed for computer virus management [21] was copied into a text-editor and rewritten for facilitating peer-to-peer, peer-to-business-to-peer, AJAX, PVP, SCP, and

TM42 network transactions [22]. Copyright protection was written into the software, such that PoryGON cannot itself be duplicated on digital C2C2B networks, but can be purchased or traded as a separate, fiber optically loaded entity [23].

To test the ability of PoryGON to add value to C2B or C2C networks and manage the full range of move-sets and systemic trades on a C2C2B network, we uploaded a finalized version with Conversion2 to a digital stock market, based on the methods of Giovanni et al. [24]. Using the primary processor language of KraGle® we established a brick-by-brick trade network comprising 10000 simulated users with even consumer priority and a simulated central Lord-Business [25] as our C2C2B network. As per the primary source data of Schlangermann et al. [26], we prepared a corporate and computational gibberish loaded text [27] that, if published, proves conclusively that the target journal is predatory [1,28]. Multiple redundant codes were uploaded to the cloud using "Bill's PC" financial transaction simulation software [28,29] and an iteration of over nine thousand bootstrapping runs was done.

To test if the system could add value to an Instagram-style C2C2B network with "influencer" consumers serving as the links between the business to the baseline consumers [30], we re-ran our analysis with an EP038 transaction simulator set, using the 'Sharpen' default settings [31]. An outline of the processing pathways is presented in **Figure 1**.

Results

In our simulated C2C2B network of 10000 users iterated over 9000 bootstrapped simulations, PoryGON successfully increased the profitability of the central Lord-Business by an average factor of 340 ± 34 percentage points with no outliers. When adding simulated Instagram-style "influencers" to the simulation, PoryGON outperformed the market by a factor of 7-10, producing a profitability increase of the Lord-Business by 855 ± 62 percentage points. The simulation surpassed

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Figure 1: Programming flow-chart of Porygon processing pathways.

The key modules inserted into the baseline Matcha City Hospital Porygon program are EP038, Consumer2Consumer [C2C], v800.8Skyfall [8008S], and Business-to-Consumer [11,13-15]. The arrow pathways mark the three instanced-derivative algorithm outcomes associated with use of the Porygon module in a simulated C2C2B network.

500 teraflops of instanced calculation, but the program did not slow under this load, so its maximum optimum operating load could not be determined.

We noted an unanticipated effect when the C2C2B simulation was run that seems to operate parallel to the primary Conversion2 algorithm (Figure 1) [6,11]. The well-integrated model produced an unanticipated trade hyper-accumulation in no less than 600 of the 10000 simulated consumers per iteration, causing them to purchase beyond their means and crashing these users. The rest of the simulated consumers continued to operate with no disruption and the simulation did not stall or reset.

Discussion

Porygon's simulated results in a C2C2B network are equivalent to the Massachusetts Institute of Technology's ArbOK® stock market software in terms of financial income stream actualization [5], except their program is only built to handle C2B transactions. Porygon provides an actionable and utilization-ready value-added model for use in C2C2B systems [4]. Our data suggests the following tentative applications: online stock exchange, online gambling, online purchases from centralized distributors as in Amazon, [31,32], and wireless exchange of digital items and coupons as in services such as Steam, Bill's PC, and the Global Trade System.

Regarding the trade hyper-accumulation effect: When triggered, the original anti-virus delivery software ran Blast {} code (Figure 1), followed by a rescue algorithm intended to seal unintended or illegal trade windows in a digital trade and transfer system. This appeared to have the unintended side effect of causing a cascade effect to the underlying simulated stock market's code and triggering the external seizure.exe subroutine from the Edgarware® virus hunter package [33]. While problematic, the effect obviously cannot happen in a real world system of human consumers and is an unanticipated side effect of two similarly compiled programs running in contrapositive.

An anticipated benefit of Porygon is its ability to handle over 500 teraflops of turnkey raw bandwidth [6,9], which is an asset in dealing with multiprocessor and second-by-second transactions

as in real-world stock micro-exchanges, appositional retrospective banking counters, international currency pricing valuation and re-valuation, predatory publishing of non-peer reviewed texts, and user-driven commodities speculation. The innovative feature-set of the Conversion2 upgrade is user-friendly and can be easily adopted into non-English language platforms, with the Singapore Exchange (SGX) already vowing to apply Porygon to treasury bond, mutual fund, and regional pokemon trading to connect the central market with brokers and portfolio holders [34].

In summary Porygon is a successful, proprietary module for management and security of C2C2B trading and exchange software that has demonstrated, albeit in simulation, significant benefits to the businesses running the system? We are currently preparing upgrades for the program that can handle more sophisticated networks. These upgrades will not require re-installation of the Porygon software, but rather modify the source code directly, and will be available through a virtual disk image. We anticipate a Porygon-2 model that runs more smoothly for higher-volume networks, and a Porygon-Z model that handles multidimensional exchanges and can communicate outside the network into which it was installed, and hope to publish manuscripts on that subject soon.

Conclusion

The scope of this study is to evaluate Porygon's code in the context of a consumer-to-consumer-to-business trading platform, with the limitations associated with limiting the program to simulation. A need for future research exists, including but not limited to the aberrant code of the Silph Co. variant that shuts down Saffron City brawlers, designing a patch for the problematic seizure.exe code, investigating the prevalence of predatory journals in academia, and extending into the possibility of using the code in space exploration research.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors have no conflicts of interest to declare.

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